

Yoga & naturopathy: A path for reversal of life style diseases

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Abstract

Lifestyle diseases include Non-Insulin Dependent diabetes Mellitus, Secondary Hypertension, Cardiac diseases, Neoplasms, Obesity, COPD, Osteoporosis, and Depression. Lifestyle diseases are because of the Improper diet (High fat and sugary food), disturbed dietary patterns, Lack of exercise, Anxiety & Stress, Bad habits like Smoking, drinking, uncontrolled desires, unhealthy sleep patterns. The journey of India from the 20th century to the 21st century, has witnessed the shift from a period dominated by infectious diseases, childhood and maternal deaths to the period dominated by lifestyle diseases. In 2017, India witnessed 61.8 per cent deaths due to lifestyle diseases. As per Utton Rafei Regional director of WHO 80 % of cardio pulmonary disease, 90% of Non-insulin dependent Diabetes Mellitus and one third of cancers can be avoided through a change in lifestyle or adapting the lifestyle that keeps you and your family healthy and happy. Yoga is a scientific approach of how to keep one's body fit and mind Calm and composed. It tells you what to eat; how to eat; when to eat; what to avoid. Naturopathy is based on using five elements Earth, Fire, Water, Air and Akasha to rejuvenate, revitalize and strengthen our immune system. Using both Yoga and naturopathy we can definitely reverse from the lifestyle diseases. This can be achieved by daily practising yoga exercises, Pranayama, Use of natural medicines, and Amendment of sleep patterns, appropriate tailor-made diet and Modification in eating patterns.

Keywords: Lifestyle diseases, yoga, naturopathy, sleep pattern, diet

Introduction

The journey of India from the 20th century to the 21st century, has witnessed the movement from a period dominated by infectious diseases, childhood and maternal deaths to the period dominated by lifestyle diseases. In 2017, India witnessed 61.8 per cent deaths due to lifestyle diseases [1]. According to Indian Council Of Medical research [ICMR] and other institutes which conduct studies on lifestyle diseases all deaths due to Non-Communicable diseases has increased from 37.09% in 1990 to 61.8% in 2016 [2]. India ranks second after China in global diabetes epidemic with 77 million people with Diabetes mellitus [3]. 60-70% Indians with hypertension unaware of their condition. India is third after China and United states for Cancer. As per Utton Rafei Regional director of WHO 80 % of cardio pulmonary disease, 90% of Non-insulin dependent Diabetes Mellitus and one third of cancers can be avoided through a change in lifestyle or adapting the lifestyle that keeps you and your family healthy and happy.

Meaning of lifestyle diseases

The Lifestyle diseases or Non-communicable diseases include Typ-2 diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, Cardiovascular diseases, Cancer, Obesity, COPD, Osteoporosis, Depression and many more. The above diseases are called lifestyle diseases because they are due to modified lifestyle behaviour such as Improper diet (High fat and sugary food), disturbed dietary patterns, Lack of exercise, Anxiety & Stress, Bad habits like Smoking, drinking, uncontrolled desires, unhealthy sleep patterns, sedentary work, long hours of watching television couch (potato), digital addiction or children addicted to gaming. Indirectly we can said that we are paying a price or cost at

the physical and mental level while using gadgets to do our housework, using vehicles instead of walking a short distance, Using packed food instead of fresh food, Running a rat race to be better than others, quality of food consumed is more in calories with less nutritive value and many more reasons.

Causes of lifestyle diseases

According to the Indian journal of Occupational and environmental medicine [7]

1. Easy availability of Low cost junk food.
2. Physical inactivity.
3. Sedentary life-long sitting hours.
4. Western lifestyle –watching television and mobiles for long hours.
5. Convenience of fast food and home delivery.
6. People working in late night shifts.
7. Disturbance in eating habits.
8. Late night parties and buffet dinners where person has to stand and eat.
9. Excessive stress.
10. Smoking and alcohol consumption.
11. In a Single child in the family, the child has no one to share his feelings leading to depression and anxiety.
12. Both the parents are working therefore easily prone to eating processed and packed food.
13. Children prefer mobile or video games rather than outdoor sports.
14. Internet addiction.
15. Artificial Intelligence is making the services to the mankind very easy, whether a blessing or curse is a topic of debate but indirectly affects the lifestyle of humans.

16. Poor nutritive foodstuff.
17. More consumption of freeze food rather than fresh consumption of food.
18. Reduction in Dietary fibre and increase in dietary glycaemic load may contribute to obesity ^[6].

Who is affected by lifestyle diseases?

The Comprehensive National Nutrition Survey (CNNS) revealed that Indian youth aged 5-19 are showing early signs of Diabetes, Hypertension and Obesity. The Indian journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism says that somewhere between 5.74% and 8.82% of school children in India are obese have hypertension and are prone to heart ailments. Thus lifestyle diseases affects all age groups and has no gender discrimination

Why are we concerned about lifestyle diseases? Just take anti-hypertensive or anti diabetic pill for life-time!

We should be more concerned as Lifestyle diseases result in

1. loss of independence,
2. Years of disability or death.
3. Impose burden on the family
4. High cost health care services – Medical debt and bankruptcy.
5. Affects Inter-personal Relationships.
6. Psychological distress like helplessness and lack of control felt by family members.
7. Inhibit the educational attainment of children in the family.

Knowing that the lifestyle diseases are the slow and silent killers ONE should begin to change their lifestyle even before the person is diagnosed with either one of the lifestyle diseases or even if in pre-hypertension or pre-diabetic phase. Health care costs are out of control; let's try to deal with the real causes.

Exactly what should be considered as the ideal lifestyle?

Following points emphasize on ideal Lifestyle

1. Doing what you Love.
2. Happy and contented with whatever is available to you.
3. Becoming someone that makes you proud about yourself.
4. Stress free life.
5. No anxiety about future or guilt of past.
6. Enjoying time with loved ones
7. Daily Meditation or Prayers to be done.
8. Having a positive attitude in all aspects of life.
9. A feeling of being wanted and respected in the society.
10. Having a family to share your feelings.
11. A healthy competition at the work place or school or university
12. Respect for Good values.
13. The definition of perfect lifestyle will differ from person to person but in general can consider happy soul in a healthy mind and body.

Do we really follow or have the above points in the Rat-race to earn the daily living?

The answer is No and the situation cannot be changed now. Yes it is very difficult to revert back to the life free from the needs, demands and rat race for money or from simple village which we 95% of Indians came from . With the western pattern of education even a small child has stress

with academic performance and develops inferiority complex. The 21st century Parent is more obsessed with the child's academic performance rather than his mental well-being.

Then how do we free ourselves from Lifestyle diseases?

The answer is **yes** we can free ourselves from Lifestyle diseases by following the path of Yoga and Naturopathy. Following are the key points which any individual suffering from Lifestyle diseases can follow and revert back to fit body and mind.

Following steps are based-

Lifestyle diseases affect any age group from 5-6 years onwards and both sexes.

After doing all the haematological tests and Biochemistry tests suggested by Physician note the required parameters of following

1. Weight for your height,
2. BMI- Body Mass Index required for your height
3. BSL – Blood sugar Level values and Serum Insulin levels.
4. HbA1C
5. Blood pressure required for your age.
6. Bone density for your age.

Now having known how much you have work for bringing back the body to the homoeostasis balance) you follow the below suggested path. You should consult Expert Yoga Teacher or Naturopathic Physician or any Medical Physician to explain what the normal parameters are required for or body. Study your own body requirements and daily routine and on that basis make a schedule of the following

A. Yoga: Begin with regular exercises – At least 03 sessions per week initially & later make it a regular daily basis activity.

1. First chant at least 5 Omkaras: Pray to the Guru and then begin with asanas
2. Warm-up exercises of neck, shoulder, hands, waist, legs followed by
3. Sitting asanas: Gomukha asanas. Ardhakati chakra asana, ushtra asana, shashaha asana.
4. Standing asanas: Trikona asana, Tadasana, Padottana asana, Hasatapada asana, mehru asana, padangusta asana,
5. Supine position lying on the back–Matysa asana, pavanamukta asana, eka/ dwipada uttanpada asana, Nauka asana.
6. Prone position lying on the stomach Ardha salbha asana, Bhujang asana, Dhanurasana,
7. Asanas help to maintain balance, posture and regulates the baro-receptor reflex mechanism that controls the blood pressure ^[5].
8. Pranayama: Breathing exercises Anoloma Viloma, Bhramari, Bastrika, This helps to reduce the sympathetic over-activity and reduce stress therefore relaxes the mind and body
9. Mudras: Viparit karni mudra, Brahma mudra they have action on the neuro-endocrine system and helps in secretion of good hormones.

B. Naturopathy: Naturopathy is using daily food as medicine

Early morning

Detox drink - Warm water with Lime juice or spice tea/ cardamom boiled in water. Can add 1/4th tsf of jaggery to the above drink if the person is non-diabetic

After half an hour Micro nutrient ingestion – almonds, walnuts, seeds Best when soaked over-night and the consumed)

Breakfast high protein and less carbohydrate – Here are few suggestions

Boiled or less oil fried eggs, mixed grain and pulses Thalipeeth, Upma, Pohe with more fibre vegetables added like carrots, peas, beet-root, pomegranate etc.

Any one Fruit with low glycaemic index for diabetic patient) after breakfast.

Lunch:- Salads Cucumber/carrots/radish/ onions/ lettuce/ first then Millet/ jowar/bajra Bhakri Indian bread) and vegetable plus any pulses dal curd/buttermilk homemade, sesame/coconut/ groundnut chutney in small quantity.

4 pm snack: - Chana, makhana, murmura Puffed rice) plus green tea.

7-8 pm dinner – Vegetable soup/ Ckicken soup, Moong dal or chila or sprout bhel or paneer Homemade Indian cheese). Avoid rice or grains in the night.

Alkaline drink before sleep Water with PH >7.0) Jeera Cumin) water.

Keeping yourself well hydrated.

Above diet plan is just an example that can be followed under the guidance of Expert naturopathy consultation is a must. A tailor made diet can be prepared depending on the diseases and resources available to the patient. The naturopath will understand the body type and advice diet accordingly

C. Sleep: Sound sleep of 6-8 hours is must and rejuvenates the body. Omkar chanting helps the patients with insomnia or disturbed sleep. Consult the yoga expert or naturopathy physician for the advice.

D. Mind: Most important keeping yourself positive and happy contributes to the reversal of the lifestyle diseases.

E. Time of consumption of food: Breakfast, Lunch and Dinner timings should be fixed. Eating before sunset is a good habit or try eating before 8:00 pm and after half an hour go for a walk.

For preventing the sufferings of lifestyle diseases one should imbibe good values in the family, follow daily practise of yoga, and eat nutritive food.

Above points is the path to reverse you from the lifestyle diseases. Pre-requisites for reversal or prevention of lifestyle diseases is

- Awareness of your own mental state and body needs.
- Having a positive attitude.
- Self –motivation.
- Strong Will power and persistence
- Patience and strong belief that you can reverse the lifestyle disorder with the help of Yoga expert or Naturopathy expert.

Our Indian culture always followed the Healthy lifestyle. Due to Western Invasion and their imitation we are forgetting our culture. My hope is to restore the healthy lifestyle. Yes with yoga and naturopathy it is possible

Challenges while following the above path

1. **Time:** Time required for reversal from any of the lifestyle diseases will vary from person to person, his or her immunity 2-3 months to 1-2 years. Hence patience is mandatory
2. **Junk food:** Easily available anywhere at the phone call distance
3. **Refined food:** Easily available –Maida, Refined oil, refined sugar etc. Any food that is refined has lost its nutritive value.
4. Both parents are working thus child is prone to eat junk and packed food.

Even with the above challenges we can reverse from the lifestyle diseases by following the path of yoga and naturopathy.

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